

CLASSIFICATION OF PROVINCES IN INDONESIA BASED ON OCCUPANCY RATE OF STARRED HOTEL ROOMS USING CLUSTER METHODS HIERARCHY

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Abstract

The condition of Indonesia as an archipelagic country that has rich natural wealth and beauty abundant. The wealth and beauty of this nature should be used as best as possible in order to become a source of state revenue, one of them through the field of tourism. Armed with the natural beauty that is owned, Indonesia became one of the countries that become the destination of tourists. Thus the hotel has an important meaning for tourism activity in Indonesia. Therefore the quality of hotels in Indonesia needs to be improved, and then to know the quality of hotels in Indonesia needs to be grouped. The grouping is done on 34 provinces in Indonesia based on star hotels category. The purpose of this five star hotel classification is to know the occupants of the highest star hotels in each Province and then to know which star hotels should prioritize quality improvement. Result of the groupings obtained from the cluster analyze using hierarchy method is cluster 1 consists of Bengkulu, cluster 2 consists of North Maluku, cluster 3 consists of North Kalimantan, cluster 4 consists of Central Sulawesi and Gorontalo and 29 other provinces are in cluster 5.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2582317

1. Introduction

Indonesia is an archipelago country that has the wealth and beauty of nature. Wealth can be used as a source of State revenue, one of them through the field of tourism. Indonesia has more than 17,508 islands and each island has different potential, especially in the field of tourism.

The development of Indonesia's tourism sector is now beginning to grow again, after all this time the Indonesian nation is shaken by a prolonged crisis. The Government is aware that Indonesia has so many potential tourist attractions that can be sold to increase foreign exchange. The potential for uprooting includes: natural scenery, cultural diversity, customs, and hospitality of Indonesians.

Armed with the natural scenery and cultural diversity that is, so the state of Indonesia is one of the countries that become tourist destinations. And then to enhance the role of tourism, strongly related between tourism objects with facilities and infrastructure that support it in the tourism industry, as well as hospitality.

The tourists who come to Indonesia certainly want to enjoy the natural atmosphere with a sense of security, comfortable, fun, and memorable, and does not rule out the possibility, that both foreign and domestic tourists would require various conveniences such as

transportation, food and beverage, service, and lodging . Thus, the role of the hospitality sector has significance for tourism activities.

Hotel can be defined as a company that provides services in the form of accommodation (lodging) as well as serving dishes and facilities for commercial purposes. Hotels in Indonesia are numerous, so categorizing hotels into several types based on the stars they have. Each city has almost a star hotel, ranging from 1 star, 2 star, 3 star, 4 star, up to 5 stars.

Today the hospitality business is growing and developing in Indonesia. The number of tourist destinations and hotels is increasing in many areas. Hotel development is intensified in 2015-2018 in various regions, especially in Jakarta and Bali as benchmark areas as well as with quality improvement in the hotels. Development and quality improvement may be lacking and or not appropriately done if it is done without careful analysis. Suppose the construction of a 3 star hotel in Bandung continues to be done, but based on the article tempo.co [12] in 2015 ago the number of hotel visitors in Bandung dropped dramatically. A top three-star hotel that typically has a residential rate of up to 70 percent, now down to 35 percent. Thus the analysis is necessary, so that development and quality improvement can be done properly.

Based on the above description, the authors are interested to analyze the problem using clustering analyze. The results of the analysis will provide information about the occupants of the highest-rated hotels in each province and then be able to know which star hotels should prioritize quality improvement. Thus the title of the paper raised is "Grouping of Provinces In Indonesia Based on Occupancy Rate of Starred Rooms Using Cluster Method Hierarchy".

2. Research Method

2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analysis is a way of describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make conclusions that apply to the general / generalization. The characteristics of descriptive analysis, namely the presentation of data is more emphasized in the form of tables, graphs, and statistical measures, such as percentage, average, variance, correlation, and index numbers. In addition, this analysis does not use the significance test and the error rate because there is no generalization error [6].

2.2 Clustering Analysis

Group analysis or commonly known as cluster analysis found by J.MacQuenn is one statistical technique that aims to group objects into a group such that objects that are in one group will have a high similarity compared to objects that are in other groups . [10] The process of group analysis is the grouping of data that is done with two kinds of methods that is hierarchy method and non-hierarchy method. In the non-hierarchy method, the number of groups has been determined first. While the hierarchy method is used when the number of groups is determined based on the results of the analysis. The hierarchical method is a structured and gradual grouping method based on the resemblance of properties between objects. The similarity of these properties can be determined from the proximity of the distance .[4]. The application of this cluster is very much, because almost in identifying problems or decision-making is always not exactly the same but tend to have similarities only. [9] The purpose of grouping a set of object data into groups with certain

characteristics and distinguishable from each other is for further analysis and interpretation in accordance with the research objectives undertaken [3].

2.3 Cluster Hierarchy Method

Clustering process using hierarchical procedure is based on the concept of treelike structure. This concept begins by combining the two most similar objects, and then the two objects join together again with one or more other most similar objects. And so on so that there is a sort of hierarchy (sequence) of the objects that make up the cluster.

The sequences can be analogous to the tree (treelike) that starts from the roots, stems, branches, leaves, and so on, which branches. Logically, the clustering process will eventually 'clump' into a large cluster that includes all objects. This method is called agglomerative methods, which can be described by dendrogram.

Steps to cluster hierarchy:

1. Identify items with the closest distance
2. Combine the item into one cluster
3. Calculate the distance between clusters

2.4 Distance Size

Euclid distance is the most common and simple type of distance used when all variables are continuous. In this method, the distance measurement is done by calculating the square root of the sum of squares of the difference of the value of each variable. In general Euclid distance is formulated as follows [1]

Where:

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^p (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2} \quad (1)$$

Description :

d_{ij} : is the distance between object i and object k

x_{ik} : is the value of object i on the variable of k

x_{jk} : is the value of object j on a given variable

p : is the number of variables observed.

This method has the advantage that the distance of any two objects is not influenced by the addition of a new object, which may be the outliers. However, the distance can be very large, due only to the scale difference. The distance Euclid requires the assumption that among the variables are not correlated and the units used are the same. For data that is not the same unit can be standardized to the variables.

Another distance that is also often used is the distance Mahalanobis. The Mahalanobis distance is used if there is a correlation between the variables used, so this distance depends on the matrix of the variety of the uniform. To adjust the difference of variance and covariance between p variables, the statistical distance can be used as follows:

$$d^*_{(x,y)} = \sqrt{(x - y)'s^{-1} (x - y)} \quad (2)$$

(Rencher, 2002)

3. Result and Discussion

1. The Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	Start 5	Start 4	Start 3	Start 2	Start 1
Mean	31.821471	49.347647	46.757647	42.182647	38.042941
Standard Deviation	28.340676	15.496021	13.985377	16.474699	15.911748
Min	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Max	69.540000	68.820000	64.870000	69.310000	69.860000

Based on table 1 show that, the highest rate of starred hotel rooms using in Indonesia is 4-start hotel which shown by mean of each starred hotel, and second is 3-start hotel. whereas the 5-start hotel is the lowest hotel room using in Indonesia, it means that tourism like stay in 4-start hotel or 3-start hotel better than 5-start hotel.

From the data the level of residential room hotel can be seen in the following histogram:

Figure 1. Residential rate five stars Hotel Rooms according to provinces in Indonesia.

Based on figure 1 shows that the level of the residential highest 5-star hotel rooms in North Sumatera province with a value of 69.54, followed by Papua with the second ranked 69.16 value and there are some provinces that do not have 5 stars hotel namely Aceh, Jambi, Bengkulu, Lampung, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, North Kalimantan, Central Sulawesi, Southeast Sulawesi, Gorontalo, West Sulawesi, Maluku and West Papua.

Figure 2. Residential rate three and four stars Hotel Rooms according to provinces in Indonesia

Based on Figure 2 shows the level of residential Room 3-star hotel in the Gorontalo province is the highest value of 64.87, followed by Jakarta with second ranked 63.29 value and there are some provinces that are not data 3 star hotel namely North Maluku and North Kalimantan, and the level of residential Rooms of the highest 4-star hotel in the province of Maluku with 68.82 value, followed by Central Kalimantan with the second ranked 67.35 value and there are some provinces that don't have a 4-star hotel as like Bengkulu and North Maluku.

Figure 3. Residential rate one and two stars Hotel Rooms according to provinces in Indonesia Based on the figure 5 shows the level of the residential highest 1-star hotel Rooms in Jakarta with 69.86 value, followed by the value of the Bengkulu 67.83 as ranked second and there are some provinces that don't have a data rate residential 1-star hotel room as like Central Kalimantan and Central Sulawesi. And the level of the residential highest 2-star hotel Rooms in DKI Jakarta province 69.31 value, followed by Lampung Province as second ranked 68.67 value as well as several provincial-level data that aren't residential room 2-star hotel that is central Sulawesi and Gorontalo.

2. *Cluster Analysis*

The main purpose of the analysis of the cluster is to classify objects based on similarity of characteristics between the objects. The object will be classified into one or more clusters (groups) so that the objects that are in a cluster will have similarities with one another [9]. The clustering method used i.e. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis. Dendrogram obtained as follows:

Figure 4. Dendrogram Group

Visually as in Figure 6 group formed by as much as 5. The cluster member has been obtained as follows (the number sequence of the province can be seen in annex 1):

Table 2. Result of Cluster

Cluster	Provincses
1	Bengkulu
2	North Maluku
3	North Kalimantan
4	Central Sulawesi and Gorontalo
5	Aceh, North Sumatera, West Sumatera, Riau, Jambi, South Sumatera, Lampung, Kepulauan Bangka Belitung, Kepulauan Riau, DKI Jakarta, West Java, Central Java, DI Yogyakarta, Easr Java, Banten, Bali, Southeast West Nusa, Southeast East Nusa, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, East Kalimantan, North Sulawesi, South Sulawesi, Southeast Sulawesi, West Sulawesi, Maluku, West Papua dan Papua

The average values obtained by clustering the data presented in the following table:

Table 3. Average per Cluster

Cluster	Star 5	Star 4	Star 3	Star 2	Star 1
1	0	0	46.68	62.54	67.83
2	35.39	0	0	30.47	67.28

3	69.54	62.42	50.61	23.36	53.14
4	0	51.75	61.1	0	15.91
5	43.11	45.46	43.24	41.23	37.01

Table 2 is the Basic naming clusters used in this study has considered the amount retrieved from each factor on a residential level conditions against the cluster room hotel in Indonesia. In a ranking of each of these factors is illustrated in the graph of the Spider Diagram, would seen more obvious factors that would operate on each cluster level conditions against residential room hotel in Indonesia.

Figure 5. Spider Diagram

Figure 5 shows the characteristics of the production level of residential room hotel Indonesia in each cluster.

1. Cluster 1 has the highest level of residential hotel rooms in Indonesia is 1-star hotel, and followed by 2-star hotel and 3-star hotel.
2. Cluster 2 has the highest level of residential hotel rooms in Indonesia is 1-star hotel, and followed by 5-star hotel and 2-star hotel.
3. Cluster 3 has the highest level of residential hotel rooms in Indonesia is 5-star hotel and followed by 4-star hotel, 1-star hotel, 2-star hotel and 3-star hotel.
4. Cluster 4 has the highest level of residential hotel rooms in Indonesia is 3-star hotel. and then followed by 4-star hotel and 1-star hotel.
5. Cluster 5 has the highest level of residential hotel rooms in Indonesia is 4-star hotel, and then followed by 3-star hotel, 5-star hotel, 2-star hotel and 1-star hotel.

Figure 6. Maps of Classification

Based on the image in figure 6 above the star Hotel Distribution in province of Indonesia. 1-star hotel is located in the province of Bengkulu, 2-Stars Hotel is located in province of North Maluku, Next 3-Star Hotel is located in North Kalimantan Province, Next Four Stars Hotel located in the province of Central Sulawesi and Gorontalo and the Last Five Star Hotel Distribution of the Province Aceh, North Sumatera, West Sumatera, Riau, Jambi, South Sumatera, Lampung, Bangka Belitung Islands, Riau Archipelago, DKI Jakarta, West Java, Banten, Bali, Southeast West Nusa, Southeast East Nusa, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, East Kalimantan, North Sulawesi, South Sulawesi, Southeast Sulawesi, West Sulawesi, Maluku, West Papua and Papua. the more dark the colour it's mean that the more high the level of hotel.

4. Conclusion

From the results of the cluster by the cluster hierarchy obtained that cluster 1 is Bengkulu Provinces, cluster 2 is North Maluku, cluster 3 is North Kalimantan, 4 cluster there are Central Sulawesi and Gorontalo and 29 other provinces there are in cluster 5. Cluster 1 has the highest rates of hotel room using the namely is 1-star hotel, in the cluster 2 the highest is 1-star hotel also, cluster 3 the highest hotel room using is 5-star hotel, cluster 4 3-star hotel it's highest hotel, and the last is cluster 5 that is 4-star hotel.

5. Suggestion

From a series of studies that have been done, some of the suggestions can be done for the sake of progress and improvements to this study as follows.

1. for the regions (provinces) are expected to improve aspects of aspects where necessary in accordance with the results of the cluster in order to increase and prosper people related to the hotel, in addition to the areas of progress in particular in the the field of economics.
2. The hotel may add to the development of services for the sake of attracting tourists staying at the hotel.
3. Governments can also improve access to develop and inform the hotel frequently visited each cluster in order to interest more visitors and place more easily found or the Government can rebuild hotels starred in accordance with the interest of visitors in each cluster is particularly close to the tourist attractions because of the increase in the other hand in the field regional economies can also improve in the field of tourism.
4. the Expected results of this research can be used as material for the next research information related to clustering analysis with the method of hierarchy and the results can be beneficial to all parties.
5. Expected to the Central Bureau of Statistics can further complement the hotel's visitors so that higher level can be analyzed terhadap throughout the hotel in Indonesia.

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